

Conference Abstract

Ground beetles communities (Coleoptera: Carabidae) from the Piana degli Albanesi surroundings (Sicily, Italy)

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Abstract

Piana degli Albanesi (Sicily, Italy) is a mountain locality (800 meters above sea level) near Palermo. It is situated in a valley surrounded by four mountains (Pizzuta, Kumeta, Maganoce, Xeravulli) that ends at the lake of Piana degli Albanesi. Piana degli Albanesi and its surroundings are very important localities in the Sicilian entomological history with numerous records.

In this work, we show the Carabidae populations that live in this study area, with particular attention to the total number of species present and to their ecological and biogeographical characteristics.

Carabids are useful bioindicators, often used to identify habitat alterations; research focused on them allows obtaining different information on the environments studied.

Keywords

Ground beetles, biodiversity, Italy

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